

Correlation between Piagetian and Vygotsky's Theories Informed Strategies on Performance and Retention in Number Sense among Pupils in Katsina State

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Abstract

This study compared correlation between Piagetian and Vygotsky's theories informed strategies on performance and retention in number sense among pupils in Katsina state. The study employed quasi experimental pretest posttest non-randomized control group design, in which a total of 387 primary three pupils were selected from eight experimental (8) primary schools in eight zones of Katsina State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB) using multi-stage sampling technique. The study used a 25 multiple choice items Primary Three Number Sense Performance Test (PTNSPT) and its shuffled version for data collection. The instruments were validated by experts in Mathematics Education and Test and Measurement. The reliability of the instruments was estimated using test - retest method and reliability index obtained was 0.78 and 0.80 were calculated by the use of Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while independent samples t-test was used to test null hypotheses. The analyses were done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) at 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the study showed that; pupils taught using Piagetian approach outperformed those taught using Vygotsky's theory informed teaching, retention of pupils taught using the two approaches was similar, performance of male and female pupils taught using PTIT were gender balanced and female pupils taught using VTIT outperformed their male counterparts in retention. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that; primary school teachers in experimental schools of the study need to sustain the tempo, share and maintain the strategies of the two approaches as outcomes showed improved performance and retention and professional bodies like Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN), Mathematics Panel of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) and journals in tertiary institutions may promote the approaches (PTIT & VTIT) in conferences, workshops and publication in their journals.

Keywords: Piagetian theory informed strategy, Vygotsky's theory informed strategy, Performance, Retention, Gender

Introduction

Primary education is the education given to learners usually from 6 to 12 years of age and is the key building block for children's future education as it provides them with the basic knowledge and skills. This level of education fosters or hampers a love of learning, encourages or douses curiosity, prepares children for future academic challenges and is the foundation of a child's educational journey. It gives the child the first impression of core subjects (which include mathematics) and plays a vital role in the formation of the child's overall development. At this level of educational pursuit, children develop their attitudes to learning and form their basic social-emotional competencies.

Mathematics is a fundamental subject that plays a crucial role in shaping a child's cognitive development as it lays the foundation for higher-level Math and science and critical thinking skills essential for success in any field. In primary school, pupils are introduced to basic mathematical concepts, numbers, operations, geometry, and measurement. Mathematics is important in primary school because it is used in everyday activities and provides students with the tools to effectively navigate new situations. In addition, it helps develop students' thinking skills and plays a crucial role in mastering theoretical materials. Math helps learners to understand and engage with the world, from everyday tasks such as managing money and following recipes to analyzing data and solving problems. A strong foundation in math will better prepare students for success in these subjects.

The importance attached to mathematics in school curriculum at all levels of education system accurately reflects the role of the subject in society as asserted by Gravemeijer, Stephen, Julie, Lin and Ohtani (2017) that in a world that is changing rapidly under the influence of informatisation, automatisisation, digitization, and globalization; effective teaching of mathematics

becomes imperative to facilitate acquisition of 21st century skills. Similarly, Thomas (2018) submitted that mathematics is so important to the extent that without its knowledge there may be no development in Nigeria. However, in spite of the importance of primary education, its quality in general and that of mathematics at primary level in particular falls short of being satisfactory regarding pupils' performance which invariably adversely affects learners' retention and heighten anxiety towards the subject. Despite the importance of mathematics in the Nigerian educational system and national development, the academic performance of learners in Mathematics at national examinations has been lackluster (Makondo & Makondo, 2020). The results of external examinations have been unimpressive, specifically in the Ilorin West Local Government Area of Kwara State in 2019. Out of the 13,062 pupils who registered for the Kwara State Common entrance examination in the local government area, only 4,781 (36.6%) had 50 marks or higher in Mathematics, while 8,281 (63.4%) had less than 50 marks (Obafemi. *et. al.*, 2023)

Piaget's theory stresses the need for prioritising learning through experience instead of memorising information. Educators should challenge children's knowledge by exposing them to new experiences and information while also keeping in mind that these challenges should be matched to children's individual abilities. The difficulty level of activities and challenges should be matched to children's current ability to understand the world. On the other hand, Vygotsky, a Russian psychologist, developed a theory of cognitive development known as the Sociocultural Theory of Cognitive Development in the early twentieth century. The main assertion of the Vygotsky theory is that the cognitive development of children is advanced through social interaction with other people, particularly those who are more skilled. In other words, Vygotsky believed that social learning comes before cognitive development, and that children construct knowledge actively.

Williams (2018) sees performance more as an aggregate of several factors that indicate a student's success. Pupils' performance in mathematics leaves much to be desired. Regarding gender, Newman (2018) refers to it as the role of a male or female in society, or an individual's concept of themselves. Samuelsson & Samuelsson (2016) in research highlighted a traditional gender gap in favour of boys.

Models and instructional strategies (of learning) are designed to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of teachers in the discharge of their duties aiming to impact on pupils' learning. The groundbreaking work of Hattie (2017) gave the effect sizes of Piagetian and Vygotsky's approaches as 1.28 and 0.84 against a mean of 0.44. This study compared the effects Piagetian (PTIT) and Vygotsky's theories informed teaching (VTIT) on performance and retention in number sense concepts among primary three pupils in Katsina state in the continuous search for instructional strategies to improve pupils' outcomes. Hence, the following objectives.

Objectives of the study

The study was guided by the following objectives:

1. Compare the effects of Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching on performance in number sense concept among pupils in Katsina state.
2. Match the effects of Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching on retention in number sense concept among pupils in Katsina state.
3. Determine whether the effects of Piagetian theory informed teaching (PTIT) on performance in number sense concept is balanced regarding gender among pupils in Katsina state.
4. Examine gender sensitivity of the effects Vygotsky's theory informed teaching (VTIT) on retention in number sense concept among pupils in Katsina state.

Research Questions

The study posed the following questions for answers:

1. Are there differences in performance in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching in Katsina state?
2. Does difference exist in retention in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching in Katsina state?
3. What is the difference in performance in number sense concept among male and female pupils taught using Piagetian theory informed teaching in Katsina state?
4. Is there difference in retention regarding gender in number sense concept among pupils taught using Vygotsky's theory informed teaching in Katsina state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for testing at $p \leq 0.05$.

5. **Ho1:** There is no significant difference in performance in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching in Katsina state.
6. **Ho2:** There is no significant difference in retention in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching in Katsina state.
7. **Ho3:** There is no significant difference in performance in number sense concept of male and female pupils taught using Piagetian theory informed teaching in Katsina state.
8. **Ho4:** There is no significant difference in retention regarding gender in number sense concept of pupils taught using Vygotsky's theory informed teaching in Katsina state.

Methodology

The study compared the correlation of Piagetian and Vygotsky's theories informed strategies on performance and retention in number sense concepts among primary three pupils in Katsina state. It employed quasi experimental pretest posttest non-randomized control group design. From a population of 430,190 primary three pupils comprising 201,164 males and 229,026 female pupils a sample of 387 pupils (207 – 91 males & 116 females and 180 – 78 males and 102 females taught using Piagetian and Vygotsky's theories informed teaching respectively). The sample was selected from eight (8) experimental schools in eight educational zones of State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB). A 25 items multiple choice Primary Three Number Sense Achievement Test (PTNSAT) and its shuffled version were used to collect data on performance and retention. Both instruments were validated by experts in mathematics education and psychology. Reliability coefficients of both were computed and found to be 0.78 and 0.80 respectively. Treatment was administered where one experimental group was taught using Piagetian and the other taught using Vygotsky's theory informed teaching for a period of eight weeks. Posttest was administered to determine performance and within two weeks interval, post-posttest was administered to measure retention. Thereafter responses were marked and sorted for analysis. Data was analysed with the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 using outcomes of 381 pupils present at the time of data collection. Research questions were presented using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation while independent samples t-test was employed in the analysis of null hypotheses at the fixed probability level of $P \leq 0.05$.

Presentation of Results

The results of the study were obtained from research questions answered and hypotheses tested through analysis of test and retention scores of 381 pupils present at the time of data collection. Student independent samples t-test statistic was employed for the analysis.

Research Question 1

Are there differences in performance in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching in Katsina state?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on Performance of PTIT and VTIT Groups

Group	N	Mean	SD	Std. Error	Mean Diff.
PTIT	207	18.75	3.34	0.238	3.44
VTIT	184	15.31	4.20	0.310	
Total	381	34.06	7.54	0.548	

Source: study data collected

Table 1 shows the means and standard deviations of pupils' performance in number sense concept in PTIT and VTIT groups. The result showed PTIT group had 18.75 & 3.34 and VTIT group obtained 15.31 & 4.20 as mean scores and standard deviations respectively. Clearly the mean scores and S. Ds are different. To ascertain the statistical significance of the difference, independent samples t-test analysis was carried out.

Null Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in performance in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching in Katsina state. The summary of the t-test for the groups is given in Table 2

Table 2: Summary of Independent t-test on Performance Scores of PTIT and VTIT Groups

Group	N	Mean	SD	DF	T	P	Decision
PTIT	207	18.75	3.34	379	8.863	.000	Sig.
VTIT	184	15.31	4.20				
Total	381	33.72	6.135				

Source: study data collected

From the results of Table 2, t-value of 8.863 and p-value of 0.000 were observed at the degree of freedom of 379. The p-value obtained was 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$. This showed there was significant difference in performance of pupils taught using PTIT and VTIT. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected and it was concluded that there was significant difference in favour of pupils taught using PTIT.

Research Question 2: Does difference exist in retention in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotskian theories informed teaching in Katsina state?

Descriptive statistics on retention of pupils taught using PTIT and VTIT was considered, summary of the results is presented in Table 3

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on Retention of PTIT and VTIT Groups

Group	N	Mean	SD	Std. Error	Mean Diff.
PTIT	207	18.73	3.29	0.235	0.50
VTIT	184	18.23	4.03	0.297	
Total	381	36.96	7.32	0.532	

Source: study data collected

Table 3 shows the means and standard deviations of pupils' retention in number sense concept in PTIT and VTIT groups. The result showed PTIT group had 18.73 & 3.29 and VTIT group obtained 18.23 & 4.03 as mean scores and standard deviations respectively. Clearly the mean scores are similar. To ascertain the statistical significance of the difference, independent samples t-test analysis was carried out.

Null Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in retention in number sense concept of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotsky's theories informed teaching in Katsina state. The summary of the t-test for the groups is given in Table 4

Table 4: Summary of Independent t-test on Retention Scores of PTIT and VTIT Groups

Group	N	Mean	SD	DF	T	P	Decision
PTIT	207	18.75	3.29	379	1.324	.186	Not Sig.
VTIT	184	18.23	4.03				
Total	381	33.72	6.135				

Source: study data collected

From the results of Table 4, t-value of 1.324 and p-value of 0.186 were observed at the degree of freedom of 379. The p-value obtained was 0.186 which is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$. This showed there was no significant difference in retention of pupils taught using PTIT and VTIT. Thus, the null hypothesis was retained and it was concluded that there was no significant difference between pupils taught using PTIT and VITT groups.

Research Question 3: What is the difference in performance in number sense concept among male and female pupils taught using Piagetian theory informed teaching in Katsina state?

Descriptive statistics on performance of male and female pupils taught using PTIT was considered, summary of the results is presented in Table 5

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics on Performance of Male and Female Taught Using PTIT

Group	N	Mean	SD	Std. Error	Mean Diff.
Male	91	18.32	3.75	0.393	0.11
Female	116	18.21	3.95	0.367	
Total	207	36.53	7.70	0.760	

Source: study data collected

Table 5 shows the means and standard deviations of male and female pupils' performance in number sense concept taught using PTIT. The result showed male pupils had 18.32 & 3.75 and females obtained 18.21 & 3.95 as mean scores and standard deviations respectively. Clearly the mean scores are similar. To ascertain the statistical significance of the difference, independent samples t-test analysis was carried out.

Null Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference in performance in number sense concept of male and female pupils taught using Piagetian theory informed teaching in Katsina state.

The summary of the independent samples t-test for the groups is given in Table 6

Table 6: Summary of Independent t-test on Performance of Male and Female Pupils Taught Using PTIT

Group	N	Mean	SD	DF	T	P	Decision
Male	91	18.32	3.75	205	-0.207	.836	Not Sig.
Female	116	18.21	3.95				
Total	207	36.53	7.70				

Source: study data collected

From the results of Table 6, t-value of -0.207 and p-value of 0.836 were observed at the degree of freedom of 205. The p-value obtained was 0.836 which is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$. This showed there was no significant difference in performance of male and female pupils taught using PTIT. The null hypothesis was retained and it was concluded that there was no significant difference between male and female pupils taught using PTIT.

Research Question 4: What is the difference in retention in number sense concept among male and female pupils taught using Vygotsky's theory informed teaching in Katsina state?

Descriptive statistics on retention of male and female pupils taught using VTIT was considered, summary of the results is presented in Table 7

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics on Retention of Male and Female Taught Using VTIT

Group	N	Mean	SD	Std. Error	Mean Diff.
Male	78	17.87	2.64	0.298	0.88
Female	102	18.75	2.61	0.268	
Total	180	36.62	5.25	0.566	

Source: study data collected

Table 7 shows the means and standard deviations of male and female pupils' retention scores in number sense concept taught using VTIT. The result showed male pupils had 17.87 & 2.64 and females obtained 18.75 & 2.61 as mean scores and standard deviations respectively. Clearly the mean scores are not much different. To ascertain the statistical significance of the difference, independent samples t-test analysis was carried out.

Null Hypothesis Four: There is no significant difference in retention in number sense concept of male and female pupils taught using Vygotsky’s theory informed teaching in Katsina state.

The summary of the independent samples t-test for the groups is given in Table 8

Table 8: Summary of Independent t-test on Retention of Male and Female Pupils Taught Using VTIT

Group	N	Mean	SD	DF	T	P	Decision
Male	78	17.87	2.64	205	-2.218	0.028	Sig.
Female	102	18.75	2.61				
Total	207	36.62	5.25				

Source: study data collected

From the results of Table 8, t-value of -2.218 and p-value of 0.028 were observed at the degree of freedom of 205. The p-value obtained was 0.028 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$. This showed there was significant difference in retention of male and female pupils taught using VTIT. The null hypothesis was rejected and it was concluded that there was significant difference between and female pupils outperformed their male counterparts among in the group taught using VTIT.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the analysis of data regarding null hypothesis one indicated in Table 2 showed pupils taught using Piagetian outperformed those taught using Vygotsky’s theory informed teaching in performance on number sense concept. This outcome corroborates the work of Hattie (2017) who calculated effect size to determine the efficacy of an intervention or educational practice relative to a comparison (mean of 0.44). The effect size of Piagetian approach is 1.28 and discussion and scaffolding (Vygotsky’s approach) is 0.82. However, Lindvall, Helnius, Eriksson and Ryve (2021) in research on ‘Examining the Effects of a National-Scale Teacher Professional Development (PD) Programme on Instructional Practices and Students’ Mathematics Achievement’ reported a small but statistical significant impact on teachers’ instructional practices with no effect found on student achievement.

Analysis of the second null hypothesis revealed that retention of pupils taught using Piagetian and Vygotsky’s theories informed teaching in number sense concepts was similar. This finding supports Fernández-Cézar, Garrido and Solano-Pinto (2020) in a study on the effect of a STEM experimentation outreach programme on 5th and 6th graders reported that program effect was not associated with learners’ gender. Also, Gholami, Mohd-Ayub, Yunus and Kamarudin (2021) in a study on Impact of Lesson Study (LS) on Mathematics Anxiety and Mathematics Achievement of Malaysian Foundation Programme Students’ reported no statistically significant interaction between the effects of educational method and gender on both mathematics anxiety and achievement.

Outcome of third null hypothesis reported performance of male and female pupils taught using Piagetian theory informed teaching in number sense concepts was gender balanced. The study of Ghasemi, Burley and Safadel (2019) who did a study on Gender Differences in General Achievement in Mathematics: An International Study, revealed no statistically significant differences observed when the achievements of girls and boys in mathematics were compared. On the contrary, Oluyemo, Musbahu, Kukwil, Anikweze and Shaluko (2020) in a study on Gender Differences in Mathematics Interest and Achievement in Junior Secondary School Students, Niger State, revealed male students excelled in mathematics achievement more than their female counterparts and there was significant difference between their mean achievements.

The fourth null hypothesis testing found female pupils taught using Vygotsky’s theory informed teaching in number sense concepts outperformed their male counterparts in retention. In different stroke, Obi, Agwagah, Newen and Nwoye (2017) in their study on Checkmating Gender Differentials in Pupils’ Achievement and Retention found no significant difference in male and female retention in fraction while Oluyemo, Musbahu, Kukwil, Anikweze and Shaluko (2020) in a study on Gender Differences in Mathematics Achievement in Niger State revealed that male students excel in mathematics achievement more than their female counterparts.

Conclusion

The outcome of the study indicated that pupils taught using Piagetian approach outperformed those taught using Vygotsky’s theory informed teaching, retention of pupils taught using the two approaches was similar, performance of male

and female pupils taught using PTIT were gender balanced and female pupils taught using VTIT outperformed their male counterparts in retention.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Primary school teachers in experimental schools of the study need to sustain the tempo, share and maintain the strategies of the two approaches as outcomes showed improved performance and retention.
2. The teaching of mathematics requires competent and experienced teachers, as such State Universal Education Board/Private School Owners are required to employ, retain and incentivize competent teachers.
3. Professional bodies like Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN), Mathematics Panel of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) and journals in tertiary institutions may promote the approaches (PTIT & VTIT) in conferences, workshops and publication in their journals.

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